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ATTRACTIVENESS OF ENGINEERING SCHOOLS IN EUROPE

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Topics: How to detect and attract talents with new generations of learning technologies and networks, Talent Management

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In this session, we would like to give an overview about the attractiveness of engineering schools in Europe and try to answer to the question how to make them more attractive. Participants of this workshop will learn the experience and point of view of their colleagues from diverse European countries, and be able to identify the main factors influencing engineering schools' attractiveness.

In a context where engineering schools in numerous European countries have difficulties to enrol talented and motivated students, an improvement in their attractiveness becomes a central challenge. Attracting and engaging future engineers has become a priority, not only for engineering schools but also for the whole of society, as the chronic shortage of engineers is likely to remain a persistent problem over the next decades. Especially important for the profession is to widen the profession for people from diverse background as the needed engineering solutions are for diverse customers and challenges.

Based on the two workshops in earlier SEFI conferences and outcomes of the Erasmus+ project A-STEP 2030, we will make a critical overview of this problem in an international and multicultural setting of engineering education professionals. The workshop will start with a short introductory case study to generate the discussion between participants about the attractiveness of their engineering school. Next, based on this discussion, participants will be divided into small groups to work on the question of what makes engineering schools attractive. Each group will present their results to the others in a short oral session by reflecting on their choice and decision making process. Finally, as a conclusion of our workshop we will organise an interactive session to engage a debate amongst participants. The workshop results will be summarized in this final step by asking participants to classify these influencing factors into institutional, national and international levels by giving examples from their institutions. Additionally, we will ask whether the attractiveness is considered to be connected to gender.

Attractiveness and especially the question of how to attract talented students into STEM education and more specifically in engineering schools is one of the important

issues of Engineering Education. The importance of this question is illustrated by the fact that the attractiveness of Engineering Education is one of the top five priority themes of SEFI. This workshop will give a contribution to improve participants' understanding how to improve the current situation and attract gifted students with wide diversity.

Considering the available timeframe and to enable the active interaction with all the participants we would like to limit the amount of participants to 30 people.